

The Intangible Heritage of Milanese Music Publishing

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Abstract. This project is part of Spoke 2 “Creativity and Intangible Heritage”, Work Package 1, of the PNRR Extended Partnership 5 *Changes* program (*Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society*). It focuses on Milanese publishing of “ready-made” music in the early twentieth century. The research is based on the identification and cataloguing of collections of mood music for films, dance music for orchestras, intermezzi for theatres, café-concerts, grand hotels, and other occasions, which are the products of a specialized publishing tradition by Milanese publishers such as Ricordi, Carisch, and Sonzogno. The project aims to identify and catalogue musical documents not only for the purposes of a history of applied composition, but also as a broader contribution to the history of early twentieth-century musical culture. The main product of the research will be a database conceived as a tool for structuring, ordering, mapping, and relating different types of objects: texts, images, musical documents in notation, and audiovisual material. The database will serve as a reference tool for basic research and provide useful support for teaching and creative or applied research. It will integrate bibliographic information with innovative methods of interactive audiovisual presentation, thus facilitating the dissemination and transfer of results to students, scientific audiences, and the general public.

Keywords: Cinematic Music, Publishing, Silent Cinema.

1 *Changes*: A European Research Project

This project is part of Spoke 2 “Creativity and Intangible Heritage”, Work Package 1, of the PNRR Extended Partnership 5 *Changes* program (*Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society*), which aims to disseminate and develop cultural and scientific research for the benefit of society. Its main musicological axes are: a) the valorization of intangible musical heritage, b) the development of basic and applied musical research, and c) the medialization of musical tradition.

The project, based at the University of Milan and to be carried out over three years (2023–25), focuses on Milanese publishing of music for use at the beginning of the twentieth century. The research involves identifying and cataloguing collections of mood music for films, dance music for small orchestras, intermezzi for theatres, café-concerts, grand hotels, and other receptive occasions, which are the product of a specialized tradition by publishers such as Ricordi, Carisch, Sonzogno, etc. (see Fig. 1).

The project aims to identify and catalogue musical documents to contribute broadly to the history of early twentieth-century musical culture.

[here Fig. 1]

Fig. 1. *Intermezzi musicali a piccola orchestra per teatri drammatici, caffè-concerti e stabilimenti balneari*, Milan, Ricordi, 1897-. Courtesy of ‘G. Donizetti’ Conservatoire, Bergamo.

2 Digitizing Cultural Heritage

The goals of documenting what we could call the ecosystem of music for use in the Milan area contribute to the general objectives of preserving and valorizing cultural and musical heritage, not least through the synergy between research and private enterprises, as intended by the PNRR *Changes* project and the Italian *Piano Nazionale della Ricerca* (‘National Research Program’, hereafter NRP).

Point 5 of the Italian NRP prioritizes the digitization of processes for the protection, conservation, and enhancement of cultural heritage, focusing on the application of digital technologies and data interoperability to make heritage accessible to a wide public. The NRP guidelines recommend the use of semantic modeling technologies, which go beyond traditional databases, to enable the aggregation of heterogeneous data with different informational value.

The NRP also emphasizes the need for university research to open up cultural heritage to social participation, not only through educational practices but also by encouraging creative and expressive processes. Research can and must envision cultural architectures and environments that are accessible and open to heterogeneous social engagement. The individual and the community are placed at the center of a learning and (sometimes) re-learning process that is as inclusive and participatory as possible. Digital platforms have great potential in this respect: by developing innovative formats and multimedia environments in which to host cultural content, they can even foster a new vitality in cultural heritage and encourage greater social participation.

Within this well-defined framework, with a clear focus on the digital transition, the historical, literary, and artistic disciplines are given a precise mandate. This mandate is not merely the digitization of a collection, a score, or sound archive and its packaging in a database destined to become obsolete. Instead, the digitization of the documentary heritage of libraries, archives, and museums must be based on criteria and methods capable of restoring meaning and vitality to cultural heritage. Digitization must be complemented by the duties of dissemination, reproduction, edition, and analysis, all processed within the digital sphere. Therefore, the processes of digitizing material cultural heritage must be complemented by the parallel development of digital tools for reading, analyzing, and enhancing its content.

Based on these premises, valuable experience has been gained in recent years in the digital recontextualization of works, environments, and sonic experiences. This process allows for the documentation, explanation, preservation, and enhancement of what is offered to our eyes (and ears), perhaps in fragmentary conditions. Ultimately, this approach aims to raise awareness of a historical reading of the reality in which we live.

3 Key Issues and Goals

The first step in reconstructing the musical ecosystem of the Milan area at the beginning of the twentieth century was to establish collaborations with conservatoires (e.g. ‘G. Verdi’ Conservatoire in Milan, ‘G. Donizetti’ Conservatoire in Bergamo), archival institutions (from the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale of Florence to the Biblioteca Braidense in Milan), and music publishers (like Casa Ricordi of the Universal Music Publishing Group) for the purposes of on-site research. This fieldwork, carried out in archives and storerooms, among shelves and boxes, has made it possible to verify the state of the sources and revealed the existence of vast collections of stock photoplay music and entertainment pieces, long forgotten and now hidden away in the deep recesses of libraries and archives.

Among these materials, the discovery of a collection of thousands of pieces of music for cinematic use, kept at the ‘G. Verdi’ Conservatoire, can be considered truly exceptional. The musical material in this collection (about two thousand complete sets of instrumental parts from more than 50 Italian and foreign publishers) has been ignored until now, with part of it never having been catalogued in the National Bibliographic System (SBN). This music collection seems to be the legacy of the musician Ettore Enrico Mo (or Mio), who worked as a pianist and orchestra conductor between the 1920s and 1940s (see Fig. 2). The pieces come from stock photoplay collections, with Milanese publishers standing out, including Ricordi, Carisch, Sonzogno, Felicetti, Leonardi, Signorelli, Mediolana, and many others.

The study of this corpus of texts, largely rescued from oblivion and brought back to life, offers us the opportunity to work at the intersection of material and immaterial culture. On one hand, the collection provides a cross-section of a musician’s professional activity, including the knowledge, routines, skills, and systems of practice associated with it. On the other hand, it enables us to see how an artisanal-industrial chain, such as that of music publishing, formed the link between this individual activity and a wider ecosystem, made up of many other musicians like Ettore Mo, who were navigating a media system undergoing dramatic change.

It is important to emphasize that such publications have intrinsic scholarly importance: they epitomize the historiographical challenges of music for the media in the first half of the twentieth century, during the years of radio, silent film, and early sound cinema (I recently discussed these epistemological issues in Finocchiaro 2023 and 2024. See also Altman 2004, Anderson 1988, Marks, 1997, Pauli 1981).

Photoplay music collections consisted of original pieces with a modular, malleable, and interchangeable configuration that allowed them to be adapted to stereotypical narrative situations (see Fig. 3). The criteria of internal organization of such collections, however, have much to tell us about the everyday performative practice of musical accompaniment in cinema. Repertoires and music collections are organized according to criteria that, as their unsystematic nature suggests, are mostly practical and intuitive. One criterion might be the musical genre (e.g., serenades, marches, dances, folk songs, etc.); another might be the emotional atmosphere or mood (e.g., in a dream, calm, contemplation, abandonment, etc.). Sometimes, they merely paraphrase the agogic indication; other categories seem to be conceived *ad hoc*.

Moreover, the practice of re-using and re-functionalizing these pieces of music, constantly hovering between composition and compilation, raises ontological problems concerning the multiple definitions of the musical work, its author, and its performance. The score of a piece of stock photoplay music is not, in fact, the source of an opus in the strict sense of the word. It is not an aesthetically grounded entity, but rather a set of operational instructions at the service of a subsequent creative act: the one that will shape the musical accompaniment of a film screening in the cinema (in this regard, see the disclaimer for Franco Vittadini's *Scene Musicali*, Fig. 4).

This obliges film music scholars to go beyond traditional methods of bibliographic cataloguing. Indeed, the identification and cataloguing of a piece or even of an entire collection of stock photoplay music is not in itself useful scholarly knowledge unless complemented by an understanding of the performative practice to which it belonged. These practices are not recorded in the primary source but must be reconstructed by consulting secondary sources of various kinds, from film scenarios to journalistic reviews in specialist journals (see Fig. 5), which only in their constellation provide a comprehensive account of the film exhibition as a whole.

The inherent and constitutive multiformity of stock photoplay music leads us to believe in the need for a new research paradigm for film music, and it is here that the potential of digitization reveals its scope.

[here Fig. 2]

Fig. 2. Mail cover sent from the Bixio publishing house in Milan, addressed to Mio (*sic*) Ettore Enrico. Courtesy of 'G. Verdi' Conservatoire, Milan.

[here Fig. 3]

Fig. 3. Franco Vittadini. *Uragano*. Biblioteca Cinema (Milan: Ricordi, 1926). The autograph score notes its possible use in 'Tumultuous, dramatic scenes. Fleeing crowds. Battle scenes, etc.'. Courtesy of the Archivio Storico Ricordi, Milan.

[here Fig. 4]

Fig. 4. Franco Vittadini. *Scene musicali per films cinematografiche*, Biblioteca Cinema (Milan: Ricordi, 1926). Courtesy of the Library of the 'G. Donizetti' Conservatoire, Bergamo: «Each of these 'Scene Musicali' corresponds to a particular situation or mood and can be adapted to any scene, regardless of time or place. Their duration can be varied by means of *cuts* or optional *da capo*, and their intensity can also be adjusted to that of the action by increasing or decreasing the tone color. Only the tempo must be strictly adhered to in order to preserve the character of each piece. The duration of these 'Scene Musicali' can also be timed, if desired, to match the footing of the *films* by following the precise metronomic movement indicated for each musical scene».

[here Fig. 5]

Fig. 5. *Commento musicale* to the movie *I promessi sposi*, *L'eco del cinema*, 1925, no. 19, 288. Courtesy of Museo Nazionale del Cinema, Turin.

4 Methods and Impact

In line with the above-mentioned strategies for the medialization of musical heritage, this project plans to create a digital repository of documentation: an infrastructure that will index a large sample of compositions and then link their bibliographic information with that of other material documents—films, journalistic writings, cue sheets, etc.—to reconstruct the overall picture of their use in historical reality. The aim is to assign to each testimony the functional role it played within the cinematic show. While the first step—the identification and cataloguing of the pieces of music—can be considered useful for the purposes of a history of *composition for cinema*, the integration of these documents will contribute to a history of *music in cinema*. This will enhance the understanding of immaterial heritage by reconstructing the theoretical-practical knowledge that drove the use of musical accompaniments in the everyday practice of the silent era.

To expand the scope of the research, a comparative analysis will be conducted with other European music publishing traditions of the same period, including Schlesinger and Schott in Germany, Bosworth and Boosey & Hawkes in Great Britain, Choudens and Enoch in France, and others. This analysis will serve to contextualize the specifics of the Milanese tradition within a broader European musical publishing landscape.

A correlated result will be the reconnection of a musical heritage that seems to have been relegated to the past, even to the margins of the archives, with the industrial methods that characterize the production, distribution, and consumption of music on today's streaming platforms. These platforms are based on a standardization of musical genres and moods not too dissimilar to, and indeed historically related to, those found in the repertoires of the silent era. A bridge between these seemingly distant practices is constituted by music publishing, a sector that remains central to the music industry today.

The end result of this project will be a digital infrastructure conceived as a tool for structuring, ordering, mapping, and relating different types of documentary sources—texts, images, musical notation, audiovisual material, etc.—using web semantic modeling technologies. The infrastructure will serve as a reference tool for research and as a useful support for teaching and creative scholarship, encouraging forms of participatory interaction with non-specialist audiences. It will integrate standard bibliographic information with innovative tools for music encoding and interactive audiovisual presentation, taking into account actions for the rendition and transfer of results to students, the general public, and cultural operators. Furthermore, the collaboration established with the archives of historical music publishers, which aim to enhance the heritage of private entities—some of which, like Ricordi, are still active and play a leading role in the contemporary business scene—can build a bridge between historical-musicological research and a system of artisanal-industrial knowledge that took root at the

beginning of the last century. This system has continued to evolve and, even today, in the age of platforms and digital dematerialization, characterizes the activity of Italian music publishing brands in forms that are only apparently different.

The purpose of historical documentation is linked to that of dissemination at various levels, addressing not only the scientific community but also digital fruition and artistic creation:

1. Dissemination for scholarly purposes involves making the scanned scores available on the digital infrastructure (for this purpose, negotiations are underway with the Archivio Storico Ricordi and Casa Ricordi). This is the subject of a scientific collaboration agreement *in fieri* between this project, the Milan Conservatoire, and the Ufficio Ricerche Fondi Musicali, representing the SBN and the ICCU ('Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico').

2. Strategies for 'augmented' visualization and fruition of this repertoire will be developed: audio recordings to be listened to simultaneously with the score, possibly synchronized with film sequences from the period. The collaboration with film archives (first and foremost the Cineteca di Bologna) has made it possible to identify suitable and historically relevant films to be enhanced in operations of rendition. A rarity in this context is a view of the city of Florence (see Fig. 6). *Veduta di Firenze* is a short film restored by the *L'immagine ritrovata* laboratory in Bologna. Our participation in the Heri-Tech Florence 2024 conference culminated and concluded with the screening of the film, synchronized with an original score by the internationally renowned composer Rossella Spinosa.

3. Indeed, the most ambitious goal of the project is to revive the editorial production of music for use through the direct involvement of musicians, composers, sound designers, and digital artists, who are invited to interact creatively with these materials in audiovisual forms, live or digital, with varying degrees of proximity to historical reconstruction. Rossella Spinosa based her musical accompaniment on musical excerpts from the *Biblioteca Cinema* Ricordi, retrieved from the music section of the National Library of Florence.

[here Fig. 6]

Fig. 6. *Veduta di Firenze* (screenshot). Courtesy of Cineteca di Bologna.

5 Conclusions

The application of digital technologies offers the potential to conduct research at the nexus of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. The digital infrastructure should provide a means of linking and localizing diverse documentary sources. However, its primary function will be to reconstruct the theoretical and practical knowledge, routines, and procedural systems that drove the use of musical accompaniment in the everyday practice of the silent film era. It is a striking illustration of the necessity for tangible musical heritage to be accompanied by intangible musical culture in order to be preserved, transmitted, and valorized.

In addition to the challenges inherent to the field of historical scholarship, it is crucial to acknowledge that these publications were disseminated in a multitude of contexts, each with its own unique receptivity and social dynamics. In this framework, they demonstrate significant potential as sources of music cultural information. The repertoires of stock photoplay music can be described as a topography of musical commonplaces: a constellation of clichés and dramaturgical conventions that have shaped the everyday practice of film music and historically contributed to the standardization (and a certain sclerotization) of musical accompaniment. Indeed, the photoplay music collections were already imbued with a repertoire of musical topoi associated with stereotypical stage situations, including socio-historical settings, exotic-colonialist characterizations, the codification of gender roles, and so on. In this regard, an investigation into the dissemination of stock photoplay music in the social and cultural milieu of a multitude of performance venues would enhance our comprehension of the role of music in shaping the society of the era.

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